

Pediatric Sepsis Prediction Hackathon: Results and Lessons Learned

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Overview

Sepsis is a major cause of morbidity and mortality in children and young people. Early detection is critical to improve treatment outcomes, but current methods to predict sepsis onset are limited. PHEMS aims to address this by developing an algorithm to predict sepsis in pediatric intensive care units (PICUs). To support the development of this algorithm, PHEMS held an online hackathon using real-world PICU data. Participants were asked to predict sepsis six hours prior to clinical onset. The hackathon provided a valuable testing ground for evaluating different machine learning strategies. The results will help ensure that the final PHEMS sepsis prediction algorithm is both high-performing and privacy-compliant.

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Sepsis: A leading cause of pediatric morbidity and mortality

Sepsis is a life-threatening condition that occurs when the body's response to an infection leads to tissue damage, organ failure, or death. Children and newborns are some of the most vulnerable to sepsis. **Up to 25.2 million cases per year are estimated to occur in children younger than 19 years old worldwide.¹** A little more one in ten of these (3.4 million) result in death. In Europe, pediatric sepsis is a major concern, particularly in pediatric intensive care units (PICUs), where infection is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in children.

Although improvements in healthcare have reduced overall child mortality rates in Europe, pediatric sepsis remains a critical issue due to its rapid progression and the difficulty of early diagnosis. The **economic impact of sepsis on European healthcare systems is also significant** as early detection is often missed, leading to higher rates of organ dysfunction, longer hospital stays, and increased mortality.² This creates a substantial strain on healthcare resources.

The urgent need for early diagnosis

Early detection and timely administration of antibiotics are essential for improving outcomes in pediatric sepsis. **Each hour of delayed treatment is associated with a 4-8% rise in mortality⁴ and most deaths occur within the first 48 to 72 hours of treatment.³** Moreover, up to 17% of pediatric survivors of severe sepsis experience at least moderate physical or cognitive disabilities at hospital discharge.⁵

The PHEMS Hackathon: Predicting pediatric sepsis

The primary objective of the hackathon was to **develop a machine learning (ML) algorithm capable of early detection of sepsis in pediatric patients** using retrospective physiological data. Learning from the hackathon will be used to inform the development of the final sepsis prediction algorithm. **This hackathon was unique in that it utilized real-world data from the PICU of Sant Joan de Déu Barcelona Children's hospital.** Ethical approval was obtained to use the hackathon data.

Figure 1. Example of AUC Model Evaluation

The hackathon was hosted on the Kaggle platform (<https://www.kaggle.com>) and open to any individuals or teams with knowledge of machine learning, healthcare analytics, or related fields. Participants were provided with two data sets: a training and a test data set.⁶ A third data set was reserved for model validation. Participants had access to the data between January 13th and February 5th and were asked to predict sepsis (yes or no) six hours before the clinical onset according to the Phoenix Sepsis Score.⁷ Predictive variables in the data set included use of medical devices, drug administration, lab test results, observations recorded during the PICU stay, procedures conducted, and demographics. The primary evaluation metric was precision-recall AUC. (Figure 1).

To support participants, video tutorials and written materials were developed explaining the basics of sepsis and familiarizing participants with the data set and the platform. Throughout the hackathon participants were able to ask questions of data scientists and clinical experts in the PHEMS consortium as well as get support from fellow participants.

About PHEMS

PHEMS stands at the forefront of revolutionizing pediatric healthcare through data-driven innovation. This ambitious project is establishing a Pediatric Health Data Space (PHDS) that will enhance access to critical health data, accelerate research, and improve health system efficiency.

The PHEMS project is particularly focused on addressing the challenges posed by privacy concerns and the complexity of data sharing due to varying interpretations of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). To address these concerns, PHEMS is leveraging federated analytics, decentralized machine learning, synthetic and anonymized data, and a structured contractual and governance framework to enable long-term collaboration between children's hospitals.

PHEMS will showcase three health research use cases during the project: 1) cardiology patients' operation management, 2) sepsis prediction in patients in the pediatric intensive care unit (PICU) and 3) therapy optimization for hemophilia. These use cases will showcase the utility of the PHDS in both clinical and organizational settings and lay the groundwork for future applications.

Results and Key Learnings

There were **high levels of participation** in the hackathon with 195 registered participants making up 171 teams and contributing 6,476 submissions. The **winning model had a predictive value of 0.626**, with the second and third place models at 0.584 and 0.576 respectively.

Hackathon Participation Summary

- 785 Entrants
- 195 Participants
- 171 Teams
- 6,476 Submissions

The PHEMS Sepsis Prediction Hackathon provided a valuable testing ground for evaluating different machine learning strategies offering lessons for future implementation in a federated setting. One of the

most significant challenges observed was severe class imbalance, with sepsis cases representing a small minority of the dataset. This is one of the most common issues when dealing with real-world ICU data. The best-performing teams addressed this by applying class weights within the CatBoost model, with automatic weighting (`auto_class_weights='Balanced'`) outperforming manual tuning and resampling approaches. This highlights the importance of handling imbalance at the algorithmic level rather than modifying the dataset distribution, which can introduce bias or instability in time-series data.

Feature engineering emerged as an important factor in model performance. Teams that leveraged TF-IDF encoding for drug-related variables such as `drug_concept_id` and `route_concept_id` were able to extract early signals of sepsis onset by capturing patterns in medication administration. In parallel, extracting temporal features from vital signs and lab results using rolling statistics (e.g., 3-hour and 6-hour moving averages) allowed models to learn from patient trajectories over time. These strategies proved more effective than relying on raw features or advanced dimensionality reduction.

In terms of model selection, **gradient boosting methods—particularly CatBoost—consistently outperformed alternatives like LightGBM, XGBoost, and transformer-based models.** While more complex architectures were tested, including temporal fusion transformers and tabular deep learning models, they did not outperform simpler models that were better tuned and engineered. Automated hyperparameter optimization, especially using tools like Optuna, further enhanced performance by fine-tuning decision thresholds and learning parameters specific to the dataset.

Translating these lessons into model training in a federated learning (FL) context will require several important steps. First, **class imbalance should be addressed locally** at each FL node using class weighting, while aggregation strategies such as FedAvg may need to be adapted to account for heterogeneous class distributions. Second, **standardizing feature engineering is crucial:** all participating sites must use a shared vocabulary for TF-IDF encoding and apply identical rolling window techniques to ensure feature consistency. Third, **FL frameworks must support tree-based gradient boosting models** and enable privacy-preserving mechanisms such as secure aggregation and differential privacy. Finally, hyperparameter tuning across sites can be coordinated using federated optimization techniques that **share performance metrics without exposing raw data.**

Conclusion

The PHEMS Hackathon for Early Sepsis Prediction provided valuable insights into machine learning model performance, data pre-processing, and optimization strategies. These insights will directly inform the implementation of Use Case 2 in the PHEMS architecture, ensuring that models developed in federated environments are both high-performing and privacy-compliant.

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